

Self-Assembly Behavior of Amphiphilic Poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)-*b*-poly(2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline) Block Copolymers

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ABSTRACT: By utilizing a unique hydrophobic 2-oxazoline monomer, we report the facile and efficient synthesis of a novel poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)-*block*-poly(2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline) copolymer library via cationic ring-opening polymerization. Varying the hydrophilic–hydrophobic block ratios of the copolymers afforded good control over thermal properties such as the glass transition temperature, leading to an increase from 0 to 60 °C as the volume fraction of the 2-ethyl-2-oxazoline block increased. A solvent-free self-assembly method was employed to study the self-assembly behavior of the copolymer library. Thus, using thin film hydration, a wide range of self-assembled structures were obtained in aqueous solution. Structures such as micelles, short and long worms, and unilamellar and multilamellar vesicles were observed and characterized via dynamic light scattering and electron microscopy analysis. All structures exhibited excellent stability in solution at ambient temperatures over a 2 month period and showed thermoresponsive behavior.

INTRODUCTION

The synthesis and self-assembly of amphiphilic block copolymers (ABCs) represents one of the most extensively researched areas of polymer chemistry due to their importance in the biomedical industry.¹ Applications in drug delivery,^{2–4} gene complexation,^{5,6} and, most recently, the development of artificial cells^{7,8} have placed great significance on exploring new design strategies in the synthesis of ABCs for aqueous self-assembly. In 1999, the term “polymersome” was first coined as Discher et al. demonstrated the first example of a diblock copolymer self-assembling in water.⁹ Since then, researchers have employed the use of copper-mediated polymerization,^{10–12} reversible-addition–fragmentation chain transfer polymerization (RAFT),^{13–15} ionic polymerization,^{16–18} and ring opening polymerization (ROP)^{19–21} to synthesize ABCs of increasing complexity with desired properties by finely tuning the composition and block ratios of the copolymers. By controlling these parameters, one is able to target different self-assembled nanostructure morphologies.²² When an ABC is placed in a selective solvent, where one block is solubilized and the other block is not, the chains reorganize to form well-defined supramolecular structures in an attempt to minimize the energetically unfavorable interactions between the insoluble block and the solvent. A large solubilizing block with respect to the insoluble block will cause the insoluble block to aggregate and form simple spherical micelles. Gradually as the solubilizing block length is reduced and the hydrophobic to hydrophilic ratio increases, the curvature of the insoluble block-solvent interface changes. This in turn changes

the packing geometry of the copolymer chains and higher order morphologies such as rods, worms, and vesicles are eventually formed.²³

In recent years, poly(2-oxazoline)s (POx) have been increasingly utilized in the synthesis of ABCs due to the incomparable level of control and functionalization over the chemical and physical properties of POx-based materials.²⁴ Functionality can be easily introduced at both ends of the chain, as well as the side chain, allowing for easy postpolymerization modification.^{24,25} Furthermore, by controlling the length of the side chain of the polymer, one can control the hydrophilicity of the polymer.²⁶ The vast customizability of POxs makes them a suitable polymeric platform for the preparation of self-assembled nanostructures.

POx-based ABCs have been synthesized via a wide-range of approaches such as sequential monomer addition,^{16,17,27} click chemistry,^{28–30} and radical chain extension of an end-functionalized POx-macroinitiator.^{31–33} The majority of self-assembly studies involving POxs have focused on using small side chain (C₁–C₄) oxazolines and/or phenyl oxazoline. While these represent the most widely and commercially available

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monomers, investigations into longer chain, more hydrophobic POxs could offer new and more exciting self-assembled structures with unique chemical and physical properties. Daubain et al. synthesized libraries of AB and ABC block copolymers containing a branched, long chain hydrophobic 3-ethyl-2-heptyl-oxazoline (EHOx) monomer. AB diblock copolymers of PEO–PEHOx exhibited unique aqueous self-assembly behavior forming new, previously unreported structures such as pseudovesicles and yolk–shell nanoparticles.³⁴ On the other hand, ABC triblock copolymers of PEO–PEHOx–PEtOx formed asymmetrical “patchy” polymer-somes.³⁵

In terms of other long chain hydrophobic 2-oxazoline monomers being employed in self-assembly studies, few examples exist in the literature with OctOx,³⁶ NonOx,³⁷ DecOx,³⁸ and Soy-based fatty acid oxazoline (SoyOx)^{39,40} being reported. Alternatively, fatty acids/lipids have been used to functionalize hydrophilic POx homopolymers to prepare amphiphilic macromolecules.^{41–44} Fatty acids are a versatile starting material, as they exist in a variety of saturated/unsaturated and linear/branched forms. Furthermore, they are bioderived and represent a more sustainable way to synthesize polymeric materials.⁴⁵ With this in mind as well as the success of EHOx as a hydrophobic block in forming unique nanostructures in aqueous solution, we believe that the use of a branched, fatty acid-based hydrophobic block could yield a broad range of well-defined and potentially unique nanostructures.

Herein, we report the use of a branched, 17 carbon isostearic acid–based oxazoline monomer in the synthesis and self-assembly of the novel diblock copolymer poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)-*b*-poly(2-isostearic-2-oxazoline) (PEtOx-*b*-PiStOx) via one-pot sequential monomer addition. DSC and TGA analyses were utilized to examine the thermal properties of the block copolymer library. From this, we decided on the use of a solvent-free self-assembly preparation method. Thin-film rehydration yielded a broad spectrum of self-assembled nanostructures. The combined use of DLS, conventional TEM, and cryo-TEM were employed to characterize micellar, worm-like and vesicular nanostructures including unique “multionion” vesicles. Finally, we demonstrated that the self-assembled nanostructures exhibited excellent aqueous stability at ambient temperatures and thermoresponsive behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. 2-Ethyl-2-oxazoline 99+% (Acros Organics, EtOx) was dried over calcium hydride and distilled under reduced pressure prior to use. 2-Isostearic-2-oxazoline (iStOx) was provided by Infineum UK and was distilled and stored under N₂ prior to use. Methyl *p*-toluenesulfonate 98% (Aldrich, MeTos) was distilled under reduced pressure and stored under nitrogen. Extra dry acetonitrile with molecular sieves 99+% (MeCN) was purchased from Acros Organics.

Kinetic Investigation of the CROP of iStOx. To a large 20 mL degassed vial equipped with a stirrer bar, iStOx (5.00 g, 16.16 mmol, 50 equiv), MeTos (49 μ L, 0.32 mmol, 1 equiv), and MeCN (12.5 mL) were added and stirred for 10 min. 2.50 mL of this reaction solution was taken and added to 7 separate microwave vials equipped with stirrer bars. Each vial was degassed for 15 min and reacted for 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 15, and 20 min. Each polymerization was quenched with 1 mL of water, and samples were taken for ¹H NMR and GPC analysis.

Synthesis of P(EtOx)-*b*-P(iStOx) Copolymers. Using DP42 (P(EtOx)₄₂-P(iStOx)₁₀) as an example, EtOx (3.50 g, 35.31 mmol, 41 eqv), MeTos (130 μ L, 0.86 mmol, 1 eqv), and MeCN (7.50 mL) were added to a sealed microwave vial with stirrer bar and degassed with N₂ for 15 min. A small aliquot was taken to calculate [M]:[I] via

¹H NMR. The vial was then placed in an oil bath and the reaction proceeded for 10 min at 140 °C stirring at 600 rpm. After 10 min, the vial was removed from the oil bath, allowed to cool, and placed under a positive pressure of N₂ while a small aliquot was taken for ¹H NMR and GPC analysis. Next, iStOx (2.66g, 8.60 mmol, 10 equiv) was added to the microwave vial with stirring. The nitrogen line was removed, and the microwave vial was placed back into the oil bath for 7 min set at 140 °C. After the reaction was completed, a relief needle was inserted into the seal to release the pressure from the vial. A few drops of water were added to quench the polymerization, and a small aliquot was taken for monomer conversion and molecular weight analysis. The reaction mixture was concentrated under vacuum, redissolved in DCM, and precipitated twice into cold ether. The product was then centrifuged, filtered, and dried under reduced pressure to yield the product P(EtOx)₄₂-*b*-P(iStOx)₁₀ (4.78 g, white product).

Preparation of Nanostructure Solutions via Aqueous Thin Film Hydration. 30 mg of polymer was dissolved in 1 mL of ethanol and was added to a 20 mL scintillation vial. The vial was placed in a heating block set to 50 °C, and the ethanol was evaporated under a flow of nitrogen to form a thin film. The vial containing the film was placed in a vacuum oven for 24 h prior to rehydration. 3 mL of Milli-Q deionized water preheated to 50 °C was added to the vial and stirred (600 rpm) at 50 °C for 5 days. The nanostructure solutions were diluted down to 0.2–0.5 wt % for further analysis.

INSTRUMENTATION

¹H Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). All spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance III HD 300 MHz. Purified products were recorded on a Bruker Advance III HD 400 MHz. CDCl₃ was used as the solvent and the signal of the residual CHCl₃ served as reference for the chemical shift, δ . Data analysis was performed using TopSpin v. 3.2 software.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). The measurements were performed by using THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent. The Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity instrument was equipped with refractive index (RI) and 308 nm UV detectors, a PLgel 5 μ m guard column, and a PLgel 5 μ m mixed D column (300 \times 7.5 mm). Samples were run at 1 mL min⁻¹ at 40 °C. Poly(methyl methacrylate) standards (Agilent PMMA calibration kits, M-M-10 and M-L-10 MW range 500–120,000) were used for the calibration. Before injection (100 μ L), the samples were filtered through a PTFE membrane with a 0.2 μ m pore size. The data was determined by conventional calibration using Agilent GPC/SEC software and plotted in OriginPro 2022b.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Thermal transitions were determined on a Mettler-Toledo DSC1 equipped with an autosampler under a nitrogen atmosphere with a flow of 50 mL min⁻¹. 40 μ L aluminum pans with 5–15 mg of sample were prepared. We used an initial ramp from 25 to 200 °C at 50 °C min⁻¹ followed by quenching to –100 °C at –150 °C min⁻¹. Then, two heating and cooling cycles from –50 to 200 °C at a rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ was performed. The T_g value was calculated using Mettler-Toledo thermal analysis software and identified as a second-order exothermic transition in the second heating curve.

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). The analyses were performed on a Mettler-Toledo TGA equipped with an autosampler under an air flow of 50 mL min⁻¹ from 25 to 550 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. 40 μ L aluminum pans were used with 5–15 mg of sample. The degradation temperatures were reported as the onset temperatures calculated using Mettler-Toledo thermal analysis software.

Scheme 1. Schematic Representation for the Synthesis of PEtOx-*b*-PiStOx Block Copolymers via CROP

Figure 1. (A) Representative assigned NMR spectra (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) of DP42 as an example showing full conversion of the PEtOx block (blue) and full conversion of the PiStOx block forming the diblock copolymer PEtOx₄₂-PiStOx₁₀ (red). (B) GPC-SEC chromatograms of the purified PEtOx_n-*b*-PiStOx₁₀ copolymers DP10–DP141 ($n = 10, 21, 30, 42, 58, 84, 103, 141$). Measurements were performed using THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent. PMMA standards were used for the calibration. (C) DSC thermograms of the 2nd heating cycle of the DP10 PiStOx homopolymer and PEtOx_n-PiStOx₁₀ copolymers DP10–DP141. Measurements performed using a heating rate at 5 °C/min with each cycle ranging from –50 to 200 °C. Glass transition temperatures calculated from the inflection point of the curve and are marked as black dashes on the thermograms.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). Measurements were carried out on an Anton Paar Litesizer instrument using a Suprasil quartz cuvette (Hellman, 100-QS, light path of 10.00 mm). Samples were measured at 25 °C at a backscattering measuring angle of 175°. Each sample was measured in triplicate with 30 runs per measurement and 5 min equilibration time between each measurement. P(EtOx) refractive index used was 1.52.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Nanostructure solutions were imaged after a negative staining treatment. The samples were drop-cast on glow discharged 300 mesh carbon-coated copper TEM grids (Agar Scientific, Stansted,

U.K.). After 3 min incubation, excess solution was removed by blotting with filter paper before incubation with 0.75% phosphotungstic acid solution for 1 min. Excess stain was removed by blotting with filter paper and dried under a vacuum before imaging. Bright-field TEM imaging was performed on a JEOL 2100 Plus Transmission Electron Microscope operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 keV. All the images were recorded on a Gatan Orius 11 megapixel digital camera, and at least six areas were analyzed.

Cryogenic Transmission Electron Microscopy (Cryo-TEM). A 5 μL aliquot of the nanostructure solution was pipetted onto a carbon coated copper grid (HC300Cu, Holey

Carbon film on Copper 300 mesh, EM Resolutions, UK). Excess solution was blotted away with filter paper, and the grid was plunge-frozen in liquid ethane cooled by liquid nitrogen. The sample was then kept at liquid nitrogen temperatures throughout the analysis using a Gatan 914 cryo-holder. TEM images were taken on a JEOL 2100Plus Transition Electron Microscope operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. All images were recorded on a Gatan OneView IS digital camera, and at least six areas were analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of Block Copolymers. Factors such as solvent, temperature, and monomer sequence were considered when designing the synthesis for this copolymer library. The first consideration was the solubility of PiStOx. It has been well reported that polar solvents such as acetonitrile, sulfolane, and, most recently, biomass-derived isosorbide dimethyl ether are good solvents for CROP of 2-oxazoline monomers.^{46–48} In a study by Hoogenboom et al., CROP of a similar length fatty acid based SoyOx monomer proceeded in a living manner with first order kinetics being observed in MeCN at 140 °C.⁴⁹ A kinetic investigation into the homopolymerization of iStOx ($[M]:[I] = 60$) also revealed linear first-order kinetics (Figures S1 and S2, Supporting Information).

Preliminary test polymerizations showed that PiStOx was fully soluble in MeCN at a polymerization temperature of 140 °C, but upon cooling, phase separation did occur, which is consistent with CROP of SoyOx.⁴⁹ This leads onto the next consideration of the monomer sequence. Block copolymers (BCPs) are typically obtained via sequential monomer addition after full conversion of the preceding block. Addition of the second monomer usually involves cooling the reaction mixture and adding the second monomer before heating the reaction mixture to the desired polymerization temperature. An issue may arise if PiStOx was selected as the first block, as the polymer would separate out from the solvent and potentially hinder the addition of the second monomer if the living chain is no longer solubilized. Therefore, PEtOx was chosen to be the first block, as PEtOx is commonly known to be soluble in acetonitrile across a broad temperature range. All PEtOx-PiStOx BCPs were synthesized via CROP at 140 °C in MeCN by using MeOTs as an initiator. PEtOx with a predetermined length was first synthesized followed by the addition of a precalculated amount of iStOx monomer with no additional solvent to give a second block with a length of DP 10. The synthetic route for the preparation of the BCP library is outlined in Scheme 1. We would also like to mention that the original intention of this study was to investigate the self-assembly behavior of this poly(2-oxazoline) BCP series in nonpolar media. However, it was soon discovered that all copolymers eventually macroprecipitated out of solution after film rehydration in dodecane. Most likely due to the significant hydrophilicity of PEtOx and the highly polar nature of the copolymer backbone. Nevertheless, an aqueous self-assembly study of this copolymer series revealed extensive self-assembly behavior to which we further explored and present herein.

CROP of PEtOx-PiStOx copolymers proceeded in a fast and efficient manner with most copolymers being synthesized in under 15 min and characterized by ¹H NMR and GPC analysis. Samples taken after the polymerization of both the first and second blocks indicated full conversion of each block (Figure 1A). GPC analysis of the final purified copolymers clearly shows the increase in molecular weight evolution of the

copolymer series (Figure 1B). The compositions for each copolymer and molecular weight information obtained from ¹H NMR and GPC analysis are shown in Table 1. As observed,

Table 1. List of Block Copolymers Used in This Study Including Their Molar Mass, Dispersity (\bar{D}), and Mass Fraction (f) of the Blocks

polymer	composition ^a	$M_{n,theo}$ (kDa)	$M_{n,GPC}$ (kDa) ^b	\bar{D} ^b	$f_{P(EtOx),NMR}$ ^c
DP10	PEtOx ₁₀ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	4.1	5.6	1.15	0.20
DP21	PEtOx ₂₁ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	5.2	5.7	1.15	0.34
DP30	PEtOx ₃₀ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	6.1	7.1	1.14	0.49
DP42	PEtOx ₄₂ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	7.3	7.7	1.13	0.57
DP58	PEtOx ₅₈ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	8.8	8.4	1.24	0.65
DP84	PEtOx ₈₄ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	11.4	9.8	1.20	0.73
DP103	PEtOx ₁₀₃ - <i>b</i> - iStOx ₁₀	13.3	10.0	1.39	0.77
DP141	PEtOx ₁₄₁ - <i>b</i> - PiStOx ₁₀	17.1	10.5	1.53	0.81

^aDetermined from ¹H NMR assuming full conversion of initial EtOx $[M]:[I]$ and full conversion of 10 equiv of iStOx sequentially added, see Figure S3 for worked example. ^bGPC, THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent and calibrated using PMMA standards. ^cCalculated using block DPs obtained from ¹H NMR.

the experimental M_n values for each BCP differ from the theoretical values. The discrepancies are potentially due to the difference between the hydrodynamic volumes of the PMMA standards used to calibrate the GPC and the BCPs. For BCPs DP58 to DP141, the theoretical molecular weights are greater than the experimental values. This can likely be ascribed to the early termination of some of the PEtOx homopolymer chains when the iStOx monomer is introduced to the reaction vial. Any residual air or water introduced into the system may cause premature chain termination. The GPC chromatograms in Figure 1B highlights this phenomenon as increasingly worse tailing can be seen as the EtOx length increases. In addition, the larger dispersities observed with increasing PEtOx length may also be ascribed to side reactions occurring during polymerization. Namely, β -elimination in which hydrogen abstraction from a propagating chain produces a new proton initiated chain and a “dead” enamine-functionalized chain. These side reactions are a common occurrence when targeting high molecular weight poly(2-oxazoline)s and using high polymerization temperatures.⁵⁰ Moreover, significant high molecular weight shoulders can be seen for DP103 and DP141, indicating the occurrence of some chain coupling reactions at longer reaction times. However, for DP10–DP42, narrow molecular weight distributions ($\bar{D} = 1.13–1.15$) were obtained, indicating excellent control of the polymerization for BCPs with shorter PEtOx block lengths.

Thermal Analysis. The thermal properties of the PEtOx-*b*-PiStOx copolymers as well as the PiStOx homopolymer were investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Knowing the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the core-forming block is important, as it determines the preparation conditions for self-assembly. For glassy BCPs ($T_g >$ room temperature), solvent-assisted preparation techniques are used. For BCPs that are rubbery and more flexible ($T_g <$ room

Table 2. Size Information of Self-Assembled Nanostructure Dispersions Formed from DP42–DP141 Copolymers

polymer	$D_{\text{DLS int}}^b$ (nm)	$D_{\text{DLS num}}^b$ (nm)	D_{TEM}^c (nm)	$D_{\text{Cryo-TEM}}^c$ (nm)	observed morphology
DP42	167 ± 6	50 ± 4	54 ± 12	53 ± 14	unilamellar vesicles
DP58	148 ± 3	55 ± 2	57 ± 13	68 ± 27	“multionion” vesicles
DP84	182 ± 10	38 ± 3	29 ± 3	22 ± 3	long worms
DP103	119 ± 2	8 ± 1	28 ± 4 ^a	9 ± 3 ^a	micelles + short worms
DP141	72 ± 1	36 ± 1	41 ± 6	31 ± 4	micelles

^aMeasured values are the average widths of the worm-like structures. ^bMeasurements performed at 25 °C in Mili-Q deionized water using a backscattering measuring angle of 175°. ^cMeasurements performed on JEOL 2100+ TEM with an accelerating voltage of 200 keV. For TEM measurements, average diameters were calculated by measuring 100 nanostructures over 6 representative TEM images.

temperature), direct hydration methods can be used. For POx homopolymers, as the length of the alkyl side chain increases from C1 to C6, T_g decreases. This is attributed to the longer alkyl chains disrupting the packing of the backbones and preventing the amide dipoles from strongly interacting. POx homopolymers with linear alkyl substituents longer than C6 do not exhibit a T_g .⁵¹ Branched analogues of linear alkyl POx have also been studied, though to a lesser extent.⁵² Branched POxs exhibit a lower T_g than their linear analogues due to an increased disruption to chain packing.

It was revealed that a DP10 homopolymer of PiStOx has a T_g of 0 °C. Only a few poly(2-oxazoline)s have an observed T_g lower than 0 °C.^{34,53–56} The higher T_g for PiStOx compared to those of these monomers can potentially be accredited to the effect of side chain crystallization. The ability for POxs to crystallize increases with increasing side chain length due to better chain packing. As a result, a larger crystalline volume fraction in the polymer disrupts the amorphous phase and increases the T_g value of the polymer. However, the presence of a branching point on the side-chain end may suppress side-chain crystallization and lead to a reduction in T_g . Figure 1C shows the DSC curves of the second heating cycle of each copolymer and shows the broad range of T_g values for the copolymer series. The difference in T_g values for PEtOx (~60 °C)^{53,57} and PiStOx (0 °C) is vast and offers a customizable copolymer system where T_g can be tuned by varying the polymer block ratios. A positive correlation between the PEtOx content and the corresponding increase in the T_g content is shown. Copolymers with greater PEtOx content contain less of the branched, flexible isosteric side chains, resulting in a better overall packing of the copolymer chains, and an increase in T_g is observed. Thermogravimetric analysis conducted on the copolymer series revealed that the composition of the copolymer had no significant influence on the thermal degradation temperature (T_d). The onset T_d of the copolymer series is approximately 350 °C (Figure S4, Supporting Information).

Aqueous Self-Assembly Behavior of Amphiphilic Block Copolymers. The self-assembly properties of the copolymer series were studied extensively through the use of dynamic light scattering (DLS), conventional, and cryogenic transition electron microscopy (TEM). SAXS analysis was attempted, but unfortunately none of the nanostructure solutions provided sufficient scattering for accurate measurements. As mentioned earlier, knowing the thermal properties of the copolymer series is of particular importance as the chain mobility dictates what self-assembly preparation technique and conditions are utilized. BCPs DP21–DP141 have a T_g above room temperature meaning the polymer chains exist in a glassy state at room temperature. In this case, the use of a solvent switch method or solvent-free method at an elevated

temperature must be utilized to ensure the polymer chains have the flexibility and mobility to freely reorganize and form self-assembled structures.

A solvent-free method conducted at 50 °C was employed to allow the polymer chains to exist in a rubbery and flexible state to facilitate self-assembly upon rehydration. Briefly, known amounts of each copolymer were weighed into separate vials and dissolved in THF. The polymer solutions were heated and placed under a stream of N₂ until all of the THF had evaporated. The polymer films were dried in a vacuum oven for 24 h to yield the dried polymer films. Mili-Q deionized water that had been preheated to 50 °C was added to each vial. The vials were capped and stirred at 50 °C for 5 days to yield polymer nanostructure solutions of 10 mg/mL (~1 wt %). The nanostructure solutions were diluted to 0.2–0.5 wt % for DLS, TEM, and cryo-TEM analysis. Samples DP10, DP21, and DP30 were omitted from the self-assembly study as they macroprecipitated upon rehydration. All nanostructure diameter sizes (D) gathered by DLS, TEM, and Cryo-TEM are summarized in Table 2. By visual inspection of the vials, there was strong evidence of polymer self-assembly due to the turbid, blue-tinted appearance of the solutions, indicating the presence of nanostructures. DLS was employed first to analyze the polymer nanostructure solutions. All BCPs showed monomodal size distributions with hydrodynamic diameters ranging from 69 to 140 nm, whereas DP103 showed a major and minor size distribution at 120 and 8 nm, respectively, possibly indicating the presence of large and small aggregates. In general, as the mass fraction of PEtOx decreases from DP141 to DP42 and the overall hydrophobicity of the BCPs increases, larger structures are formed. The increase in the hydrodynamic diameter values of the BCPs suggests that higher-order structures are formed when the overall hydrophobicity is increased.

However, it is difficult to draw these conclusions from DLS alone due to several limitations. Mainly, the Stokes–Einstein model that is used to calculate the hydrodynamic radius from the diffusion coefficient assumes the nanostructures to be spherical. Furthermore, DLS tends to overexaggerate the true size of the nanostructures as it measures the hydrodynamic radius, which includes the radius of the nanostructure as well as the sphere of hydration around the nanostructure. Additionally, light scattering methods tend to overestimate the true sizes of nanostructures due to the presence of a few larger aggregates, which scatter a greater intensity of light than small structures and are given more weight when measuring the size distributions. These limitations become apparent when the DLS intensity-weighted size distributions and the number-weighted size distributions. For DP84, the intensity-weighted average diameter is $D = 182$ nm whereas the number-weighted average diameter is $D = 38$ nm. Such a large discrepancy

Figure 2. Visual overview of the self-assembled nanostructures prepared from DP141 (A1–4), DP103 (B1–4), (C1–4), DP58 (D1–4), and DP42 (E1–4) via thin film hydration. TEM (A1–E1) and cryo-TEM (A2–E2, A3–E3) images are shown including graphical representations of each observed morphology (A4–E4).

between the two size distributions suggests either the presence of a few larger aggregates or nonspherical, anisotropic nanostructures. Therefore, both TEM and Cryo-TEM were utilized to better visualize the morphologies of the BCPs in solution given the limited information gained from DLS.

Using both conventional and cryogenic TEM methods gives a better perspective of the self-assembly behavior in a dried state and their native environment. Figure 2 shows an overview of the morphologies of DP42–DP141 with representative images from both conventional and cryo-TEM, including a graphical representation of each morphology.

DP141 – Micelles. Starting with the BCP with the largest PEtOx mass fraction $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 81\%$, TEM and cryo-TEM confirmed that DP141 forms micellar structures (Figure 2A1–A3 and Figure S5). This is the simplest self-assembled structure that can be obtained from amphiphilic BCPs. The relatively short hydrophobic PiStOx blocks, with respect to the large PEtOx blocks, aggregate via hydrophobic interactions to minimize their interaction with the surrounding aqueous environment, leading to a decrease in the free energy of the

system. As a result, simple core–shell micellar nanostructures are formed. Diameter values given by DLS ($D_{\text{num}} = 36 \pm 1$ nm), conventional TEM ($D = 41 \pm 6$ nm), and cryo-TEM analysis ($D = 31 \pm 4$ nm) are in agreement with each other.

DP103 – Micelles + Short Worms. Upon decreasing the DP of the EtOx block to 103 repeat units, the overall hydrophobicity of the copolymer increases and therefore changes the geometry of the packing unit of the copolymer. The decrease in the mass fraction of the PEtOx block for DP103 ($f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 77\%$) changes the packing unit geometry of the copolymer from a cone to a truncated cone. DLS analysis of DP103 hinted of a possible anisotropic morphology due to the large discrepancy between the intensity weighted average diameter ($D = 119 \pm 2$ nm) and the number-average diameter ($D = 8 \pm 1$ nm). Further analysis by TEM and cryo-TEM revealed that the morphology of DP103 was in fact a mixture of spherical micelles and short worm-like micelles (Figure 2B1–B3 and Figure S6). DP141 forms exclusively spherical micelles with a PEtOx mass fraction of $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 81\%$, whereas DP103 forms a mixture of spherical micelles and worm-like

Figure 3. Cryo-TEM images of DP58 PEtOx₅₈-*b*-PiStOx₁₀ (diluted down to 0.5 wt %) showing the complex multilamellar and multicompartmental nature of these unique vesicles.

micelles with a PEtOx mass fraction of $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 77\%$. The phase boundary between spherical micelles and worm-like micelles lies somewhere around $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 77\%$, but it is unclear whether the phase boundary exists above or below this value. The mixed morphology observed for DP103 can possibly be explained by the molecular weight distribution of the copolymer. The moderate dispersity of DP103 ($\bar{D} = 1.39$) means the hydrophobic/hydrophilic balance of the copolymer could potentially exist on either side of the spherical/worm-like phase boundary. As a result, copolymer chains that have a larger hydrophobic mass fraction are more likely to form worm-like micelles and copolymer chains that have a smaller hydrophobic mass fraction favor forming spherical micelles.

DP84 – Long Worms. Further decreasing the PEtOx mass fraction to $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 73\%$ results in the elongation of short worm-like micelles to form much longer worm-like micelles. Similar to DP103, the large discrepancy between the intensity weighted average diameter ($D = 182 \pm 10$ nm) and the number-average diameter ($D = 38 \pm 3$ nm) obtained by DLS indicates the presence of anisotropic structures. TEM analysis revealed a complex and highly connected, fiber-like network with the presence of spherical structures too (Figure 2C1 and Figure S7). However, upon cryo-TEM analysis, several differences were noted. The fiberlike network structures were not interconnected but existed as individual and discrete long worm-like structures, which can be seen to align themselves in a fairly ordered pattern (Figure 2C2,C3 and Figure S7). Furthermore, other morphologies can be seen in the conventional TEM micrographs whereas only pure long worm-like structures are seen using cryo-TEM. The interconnected nature of the worm structures and the presence of other morphologies when analyzing via conventional TEM are likely to be a product of the preparation method used. Drying and/or the use of a negative stain potentially induces some sort of morphological change or the formation of drying artifacts.⁵⁸ In contrast to this, cryo-TEM allows the long worm-like structure to be observed in their native hydrated state. Thus, giving a more accurate representation of their morphology and solution behavior than conventional electron microscopic techniques.

DP58 – “Multionion” Vesicles. Thin film hydration of DP58, with a hydrophilic mass fraction of $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 65\%$, marks

the point at which a phase boundary has been crossed, as vesicular-like structures are now observed. It must be noted that this is an unusually high hydrophilic mass fraction of a BCP to form vesicles as they typically form at hydrophilic mass fraction values of $f = 25\text{--}45\%$.⁵⁹ Much like the previous BCPs, the large discrepancy between the intensity weighted average diameter ($D = 148 \pm 3$ nm) and the number-average diameter ($D = 55 \pm 2$ nm) DLS values point toward some sort of nanostructure anisotropy or the presence of larger aggregates. TEM analysis of the sample revealed a vesicle morphology including the presence of vesicles with a smaller inner compartment, as can be seen in Figure 2D1 and Figure S8. Due to the high vacuum of the microscope, vesicles that are no-longer in their hydrated state can appear deflated and even ruptured. It is within these ruptured shells that an inner compartment can be seen inside. Cryo-TEM further supports the presence of multilamellar vesicles, where many can be seen (Figure 2D2,D3). Similar to the PEO-*b*-PEHOx copolymer library that was reported by Daubain et al.,³⁴ DP58 exhibits pseudovesicles and yolk-shell nanostructures as well as multilamellar versions of these structures. The internal structures of these “multionion”-like vesicles are unique and complex. Figure 3 shows multionion vesicles that contain 2, 3, and 4 fused internal compartments with each compartment containing multiple lamellae. BCPs forming multilamellar “onion-like” vesicles have been reported in the literature^{21,60,61} but few compared to the complexity and multicompartmental nature of vesicles formed by PEtOx₅₈-*b*-PiStOx₁₀. We attribute the multicompartmental nature of these vesicles to the long, branched alkyl side chain of PiStOx. Strong hydrophobic interactions and possible entanglement between the long C₁₇ chains may contribute to the bilayers fusing together, as can be seen in the cryo-TEM images, which form these highly complex internal structures. Figure S10 offers a snapshot of the broad range of other vesicular morphologies that can be obtained via the self-assembly of DP58. The top-down self-assembly approach of thin film hydration and the dispersity of the BCP may explain the nonuniformity of the vesicles.

DP42 – Unilamellar Vesicles. With a hydrophilic mass fraction of $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 57\%$, DP42 represents the BCP with the lowest hydrophilic/hydrophobic ratio of this copolymer library that is able to self-assemble and not macroprecipitate. It is

Figure 4. Intensity-average DLS traces of 1 wt % PEtOx-PiStOx nanostructures (diluted down to 0.5 wt %) of (A) DP42 PEtOx₄₂-*b*-PiStOx₁₀, (B) DP58 PEtOx₅₈-*b*-PiStOx₁₀, (C) DP84 PEtOx₈₄-*b*-PiStOx₁₀, (D) DP103 PEtOx₁₀₃-*b*-PiStOx₁₀, and (E) DP141 PEtOx₁₄₁-*b*-PiStOx₁₀. (F) Temperature-variable DLS studies of DP42 (closed box), DP84 (closed circle), and DP141 (closed triangle) showing the onset of aggregation upon heating the nanostructure dispersion above the LCST.

remarkable that a copolymer with such a relatively large hydrophilic mass fraction can form vesicles. DLS analysis revealed nanostructures that were similar in size to DP58, intensity weighted average diameter ($D = 167 \pm 6$ nm) and the number-average diameter ($D = 50 \pm 4$ nm). Aggregated small unilamellar vesicles can be seen adhering to the lacey carbon of the cryo-TEM grids as well as forming large micrometer-sized structures (Figure 2E2,E3 and Figure S9). The tendency of the vesicles to aggregate onto the carbon grids is most likely caused by the overall hydrophobicity of the copolymer. As seen with DP10, DP21, and DP30 copolymers, reducing the PEtOx block any further in length will cause the polymers to macroprecipitate. Therefore, vesicles formed by DP42 are probably on the limit, in terms of hydrophilicity, of forming stable self-assembled structures in an aqueous solution. This is a surprising and unexpected result given that almost 60% of the copolymer, by mass, is a very hydrophilic polymer and thus highlights the significant hydrophobic contribution of PiStOx.

Thermoresponsive Behavior and Stability of Self-Assembled Nanostructures. To monitor the stability of the self-assembled structures in solution, the size distributions were recorded over a period of 2 months to see if any significant size or morphological changes had occurred. In general, all nanostructures exhibited great stability when left at an ambient temperature (25 °C) for 2 months. DP42, DP58, and DP103 showed excellent stability with practically no change in the DLS traces over a 2 month period (Figure 4A,B,D). DP141 experienced some broadening of the size distribution, but no significant change was observed (Figure 4E). DP84 did exhibit a decrease in structure size as well as a decrease in the size distribution and the appearance of a small minor distribution around 12 nm (Figure 4C). The profile of the 2 month DLS trace for DP84 is now starting to resemble

the DLS trace for DP103 (Figure 4D), suggesting that the long worm-like structures might be kinetically trapped. Overtime, at room temperature, the copolymer chains may reorganize into more thermodynamically stable shorter worm-like structures. This hypothesis is further supported as cryo-TEM images of the same nanostructure solution 2 months later revealed the presence of shorter worm-like structures and the appearance of micelles, which would account for the minor size distribution appearing at 12 nm (Figure S11, Supporting Information). Finally, preliminary temperature-variable DLS measurements were conducted on DP42, DP84, and DP141 to see if there is any thermoresponsive behavior of the PEtOx-PiStOx copolymer library. Previous literature studies have shown that homopolymers of PEtOx ($DP < 100$) do not exhibit a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) between 0 and 100 °C.⁶² Meanwhile, copolymers of PEtOx with more hydrophobic POxs do exhibit an LCST. DLS allows the accurate determination of the onset of this transition by the appearance of polymer agglomerates upon heating beyond a critical temperature. Figure 4F shows the change in diameter in response to the increasing temperature.

From Figure 4F, it can be observed that increasing the temperature to a certain point triggers a significant and sudden increase in the diameters of the nanostructures going from ~100 nm to 3–4 μm. The LCST values were found to increase with an increasing PEtOx mass fraction of the copolymer from 55 °C (DP42, $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 57\%$) to 60 °C (DP141, $f_{\text{PEtOx}} = 81\%$). At these temperatures, the PEtOx blocks are dehydrated and become insoluble in water. This leads to a collapse of the self-assembled structures and agglomeration of the polymer chains to form globular-like structures. Although PEtOx-PiStOx copolymers do exhibit thermoresponsive behavior, these transitions are too high for physiological temperatures.

Finally, the pseudophase diagram shown in Figure 5 highlights how one can finely tune the hydrophilic–hydro-

Figure 5. Pseudophase diagram of PEtOx-*b*-PiStOx copolymers and their corresponding self-assembled morphologies via thin film hydration.

phobic mass fractions of a BCP to access a vast range of complex nanostructure morphologies. By fixing the hydrophobic block and varying the length of the hydrophilic block, we can obtain very similar, well-defined structures that fit with the established solution self-assembly theory with the addition of a unique morphology such as “multionion” vesicles.

CONCLUSIONS

We have reported the synthesis of a novel amphiphilic diblock copolymer utilizing a unique fatty acid-based monomer iStOx. CROP of PEtOx-*b*-PiStOx BCPs via sequential monomer addition proceeded in a fast and efficient manner. The majority of the copolymer library can be synthesized in under 15 min and yielded narrowly disperse copolymers ($\bar{D} < 1.25$). Thermal analysis of the copolymer library revealed a vast range of T_g values from 0 to 60 °C showcasing the customizability of this BCP library in fine-tuning the thermal properties by varying the block ratios. DP42–DP141 were self-assembled in aqueous solution via thin film hydration to form a broad spectrum of distinct structures consistent with self-assembly theory. The combination of DLS, TEM, and cryo-TEM allowed the nanostructures to be probed with great detail. Micellar, worm-like, and vesicular morphologies were all observed as well as some unique “multionion” vesicles. This new class of self-assembled structure could potentially be exploited for the coencapsulation of hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds within the many aqueous layers and fatty acid-containing bilayers, respectively. In addition, the mechanical strength, permeability, and drug encapsulation of these unique vesicles would be interesting to study and could form the basis of any further research. Stability studies of the nanostructures revealed excellent aqueous stability at ambient temperatures over a period of 2 months. Long worm-like structures appeared to have adopted a shorter morphology in the 2 month period, but no dramatic changes were identified. We believe this novel, fatty acid-based poly(2-oxazoline) diblock copolymer offers an easy way of producing a variety of distinct self-assembled nanostructures that offer excellent aqueous and thermal stability and have potential for use in biomedical studies.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00833>.

Polymerization kinetics, TGA, NMR and GPC data, detailed TEM and cryo-TEM analysis (PDF)

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